

ISic1037

I.Sicily inscription 1037

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific (?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, (near) Palazzolo Acreide

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140515

1. [β]ασιλ [— —]

2.

Edition: PHI175490

1. [β]ασιλ [— — —]

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492664

EDCS 39102190

PHI 140515

PHI 175490

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0216 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.57

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